

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHER AND STUDENT RELATIONSHIPS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: This article provides information about the relationship between the teacher and the student in the development of the creative potential of teachers. Proposals and recommendations are given on the duties and requirements of teachers in working with elementary school students

Key words: Educational system, modern education, pedagog, attitude, teacher's creative potential, professional skill, competence, primary school student.

Processes of scientific and technical development in the world, innovative educational conditions and various risks arising in social life require a creative approach to the education system. This creates a need for specialists with knowledge and high creative potential who can adapt to the wide information space in the conditions of rapidly changing social life and market economy, who can systematically and creatively solve the problems that have arisen, who can respond to the challenges of the new era. This, in turn, requires the identification and effective use of modern educational technologies aimed at preparing future specialists for life and professional orientation in the educational system. Especially in the field of pedagogy, special attention is paid to the issues of increasing the professional potential of pedagogues, preparing them for effective organization of scientific and innovative activities.

As always, teaching is one of the most necessary and difficult professions. Choosing this, a person connects his whole life with children. He not only gives his knowledge, but also helps to find himself in this complex world, and also helps to form character and personality. Without a teacher, it is impossible to be a good doctor, pilot, or soldier.

That elementary school student with sky-high dreams will have a strong emotional bond with his teacher. This aspect places a number of responsibilities on the teacher. Another important characteristic of elementary school students is their sense of trust in the teacher, in which the teacher has a great opportunity to influence the student. The opinion of the teacher is important and strict for the primary school student. The child sees the teacher as a smart, intelligent,

sensitive and kind person. Elementary school students will recognize his position without words.

They turn to the teacher on all issues. The influence of parents, other family members, relatives and clans decreases sharply in front of the teacher's reputation. Therefore, students accept every word of the teacher as a law. Therefore, the teacher's personality and the way of interacting with the student are very important in the educational activity that is the leader in the development of primary school students. The content of education is inextricably linked with the student's interest in acquiring knowledge, satisfaction with the result of his intellectual work. This feeling is carried out by the teacher's encouragement and forms the desire to work more effectively in the student. Feelings of pride and self-confidence in a primary school student serve to acquire knowledge and develop skills. The behavior and attitude of the teacher affects the student's behavior. For the student, the teacher is the main figure that determines his psychological state, and this state affects his relationship not only in the classroom, but also with his peers in general, and this relationship, in turn, affects his family relationships shows.

Also, these relationships determine the success of his educational activities. The skill of education is related to the process of teaching and education, to the formation of a harmoniously developed personality, to the determination of a high cultural and spiritual level in them, to the high personal qualities of the pedagogue, to his sense of patriotism, honor and duty, to a broad humanitarian and humane nature. is based on the readiness of students, as well as practical skills of organizing educational work among students. Personal qualities of a teacher that determine the humanitarian factor in the educational process include: demandingness, truthfulness, honesty, kindness, politeness. These qualities should determine the importance of the teacher to the students. Personal qualities affect the ability to teach and educate. The ability to objectively control and evaluate the knowledge of learners is psychologically and pedagogically inextricably linked with the ability to teach and educate. A pedagogue should know the principles, methods and mechanisms of objective assessment of students' knowledge and skills, develop standardized tests, and have the ability to effectively use various forms of monitoring students' learning.

In addition to the above, it should be noted that the teacher's love for his profession, his perfect knowledge of his subject, his sincerity and passion in making students, especially those of junior school age, interested in reading and learning subjects, thus At the same time, his respect and unconditional love for

children play a decisive role. We have witnessed many times that due to the teacher's charm, sweetness and kindness, and in some cases, his special grace, children without realizing it, like the subject taught by this teacher, start to study this subject with enthusiasm we have been. The great thinker, encyclopedist Abu Rayhan al-Biruni said about his attitude to his profession: "When you enter the field of knowledge, your heart will be freed from the vices that seduce a person, from situations that make a person blind, such as hardened traditions, greed, competition, he needs to be freed from being a slave to greed, from fighting for his own authority". The Russian writer L. Tolstoy also expressed an excellent opinion about the teacher: "If a teacher only loves his profession, he will be a good teacher. If a teacher only loves students as their father or mother, he is better than a teacher who has read all the books but loves neither his profession nor children. If a teacher embodies love for his profession and for students, he is a perfect teacher." Therefore, in addition to professional qualities, personal qualities of the teacher should be perfect in all respects.

In short, it is the task of the teacher to systematically organize students' interest in subjects, to direct their activities and organize work based on the established system. To organize the process of teaching the basics of science in non-traditional ways, to achieve the design of the educational process based on a perfect model, to have the skills to use these projects rationally, to acquire theoretical knowledge by students in a comprehensive, thorough, deep learning can be a guarantee of formation of practical skills in them. In fact, the pedagogical technologies implemented and newly introduced in the educational process today have a single task - that is, to achieve high educational results. Therefore, we should pay sufficient attention to organizing the integration of subjects in the educational process, in order to properly organize students' interest in subjects. In this, effective conditions are created for the student and the teacher to learn, analyze and turn the theoretical knowledge into life skills.

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